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Review Article

**COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF POST-OPERATIVE INFECTIONS:
MECHANISMS, RISK FACTORS, PREVENTION, AND MANAGEMENT**

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Abstract:

Introduction: Postoperative infections are defined as infections occurring at the surgical site within 30 days of the procedure, or within one year if an implant is present. These infections can arise from various sources and can lead to severe complications, including prolonged hospital stays, reoperation, and even death.

Aim of Work: This review aims to overview the most common postoperative infections, the risk factors associated with them, and their prevention

Methodology: The review is a comprehensive research of PUBMED and Google Scholar from the year 1999 to 2020

Conclusion: Postoperative infections remain a significant concern in surgical practice, with implications for patient health and healthcare systems. By understanding the causes and risk factors associated with POIs and implementing robust prevention and management strategies, healthcare providers can significantly reduce the incidence of these infections. Continuous education, adherence to protocols, and a focus on patient-centered care are essential to enhance surgical outcomes and patient safety.

Keywords: Post-Operative Infection, Surgical site infections, Staphylococcus Aureus, Vancomycin dressing, Closed incision negative pressure wound therapy

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INTRODUCTION:

The concerns of post-operative infection (POI) have been present since the advent of surgery. The recent developments in the field of antibiotics, modern surgical techniques, increased availability of antimicrobials and extensive use of aseptic techniques have decreased the risk of postoperative complications after surgery but have not completely alleviated it.

Joseph Lister was the Pioneer in surgical asepsis. His ideologies and techniques let the medical fraternity believe in the complete obliteration of postoperative infections for a brief period. This optimism though, was very short-lived, and soon it was realized that postoperative infections still pose a great threat as a surgical complication and could lead to increased fatality rates. Post-operative infections (POI) can lead to prolonged hospitalization and increased morbidities thereby impacting patient recovery and increasing the overall hospitalization cost. ^[1]

In 2017 Centers for Control Disease and Prevention (CDC) established guidelines to reduce post-operative infection, targeting mainly surgical site infections which account for 31% of all Post-Operative infections. The main emphasis was on tight control of glycemic index and the increased use of antimicrobials. The management of post-operative infections mainly focuses on the administration of intravenous antibiotics or detriment of the surgical site, which accounts for a longer Hospital stay thereby increasing the cost for both the patient and the healthcare system. However, a detailed review will help in a better understanding of the risk factors and an estimate of the cost associated with postoperative infections. ^[2]

Risk Factors for Postoperative Infections

Post-operative infection is a multifactorial complication. A comprehensive understanding of the risk factors will help us target the areas that require precise intervention for better patient care and bring **Surgical site infections.**

into emphasis the areas that require investigation which will help in better prevention and management of POI. The risk factors can be classified into 5 categories based on patient care, surgical precision, and patient characteristics. (Table 1) ^[3,4] Some factors like the advanced age of the patient and surgical procedures like intestinal surgery are associated with a higher risk of POI. Patients with a high Charleson comorbidity index score were associated with a higher risk of PI. The Charleson comorbidity score is associated with non-modifiable risk factors of age, but some chronic conditions that are present in the score show an area of improvement concerning medical management to reduce the risk of infection before surgery. If a patient's glycemic index is controlled before surgery or cardiac optimization is done before any cardio-thoracic procedure, it reduces the risk of end-organ damage and chances of infection. ^[5]

A good patient selection criterion should be followed to increase the success rate of surgical procedures. General physicians should also be involved in the patient selection and post-operative care which assures higher success of the surgery and reduced rates of post-operative infections A good patient selection criterion should be followed to increase the success rate of surgical procedures. ^[6] A general physician should also be involved in the patient selection and post-operative care which assures reduced rates of post-operative infections. Institution-based risk factors also affect the occurrence of post-operative infections. Urban and teaching hospitals have shown a higher risk of infections which can partly be attributed to the reason that these hospitals attempt more complicated surgeries and receive more patients from critical care units.

The socio-economic status of the patient determines the kind of pre and post-operative care they will receive after the surgery and hence can also act as a risk factor for post-operative infections. ^[7]

Table 1: Risk factors for postoperative infections ^[3,4]

Patient Based	Procedure Based	Preoperative	Surgical	Postoperative
1. Age 2. Diabetes 3. Nicotine use 4. Weight of the patient 5. If the patient is on any immunosuppressive therapy, 6. Malnutrition, 7. Colonization of methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA) 8. Duration of hospitalization	1. Type of procedure 2. Wound classification 3. Surgeon's experience and skill	1. Hair removal 2. Skin preparation of the patient 3. Hand/forearm preparation of the surgical team 4. Antimicrobial prophylaxis	1. Environment of the operating room 2. Surgical instruments 3. Duration of the surgery 4. Surgical Asepsis 5. Surgical Attire	1. Incision care 2. Postoperative antimicrobial therapy

For a better evaluation and discussion of the term surgical site infections, it is important that we first understand the standard criteria that define the term surgical site infection (SSI).

The US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) has standardized the definition of SSI classifying it into three categories. [Table 2]. This classification must be used to maintain a common understanding of the term which can further help in the development of standardized management techniques. ^[8]

	Superficial SSI	Deep Incisional SSI	Organ/Space infection SSI
Timing	Occurs in 30 days	Occurs in 30 days or 1 year in case of implant placement	Occurs in 30 days or 1 year in case of implant placement
Location	Infection seen on the skin and subcutaneous tissue around the incision (Fig 1)	Soft tissues in the deeper layer of the incision like the fascial and muscular layer is affected	Areas other than the surgical incision site
Clinical aspect	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Putrid discharge - The aseptic sample of fluid or tissue contains organisms - Signs of inflammation is present and deliberate opening of the incision is done by the surgeon unless the culture is negative. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Putrid discharge is seen from the incision site and its deeper layers but nothing is seen from the space/organ. - Spontaneous dehiscence of the deep incision or deliberate opening in case of any sign of inflammation, unless culture is negative. - A direct examination or a histopathological and radiological examination or reoperation shows evidence of abscess and infection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Putrid discharge is seen when a drain is placed in the space/organ - The aseptic sample of space or organ contains organisms - A direct examination or a histopathological and radiological examination or reoperation shows evidence of abscess and infection - A clinician's confirmed diagnosis of space/organ infection

Table 2: Categorisation of Surgical site infection according to CDC ^[8]

Figure 1: Surgical site infection seen around a midline wound showing the cardinal signs of inflammation. ^[9]

SSI and Staphylococcus aureus

S Aureus has shown the maximum association with orthopedic surgical site infection. The main source of the organism is presumed to be the adjacent skin or the environment of the operating room. Any breach in the sterile technique, inadequate decontamination during skin preparation, or inappropriate prophylactic antibiotic coverage can be associated with increased or prolonged occurrence of S Aureus. In the case of latent surgical site infections, the bacterial strain is presumed to be present in the bloodstream and any suppression in the immune response of the patient triggers the organism to cause infection. ^[10]

A preventive measure being followed currently after spine surgery is to apply vancomycin at the end of the surgery. Even though the randomized control trials have been inconclusive, the mechanism of action for vancomycin can be described as a trade-off scenario which is seen in these cases where the Staphylococcus aureus is replaced by polymicrobial gram-negative organisms. 45% of the spinal surgical site infections have shown to be associated with S Aureus but the exact source of these organisms is unclear and the adjacent skin or contaminated armamentarium is presumed to be the source. The preventive strategies used in most surgeries do reduce environmental wound contamination, but no culture-based evidence is seen that can cause lower surgical site infections. ^[11]

The Trojan horse hypothesis has been used to explain the pathogenesis of SSI. This hypothesis states that the immune cells take pathogens from remote areas (like teeth, gums, or GI tract) and bring them to the wound site. The Trojan horse hypothesis has been used to explain the pathogenesis of SSI. ^[12] This hypothesis states that the immune cells take a pathogen from remote areas like teeth, gums, or GI tract and bring it to the wound site. Gravin et al conducted a study on rats and observed that methicillin-resistant S aureus (MRSA) present in the rat gut was taken up by the immune cells and was later seen in the wound site. This hypothesis explains reduced SSI in patients where oral hygiene has been maintained before surgery. ^[13]

Preventive strategies for post-operative infections

A complete alleviation of SSI cannot be achieved. Hospitalization and surgery come with an inherent risk of idiopathic and post-operative infection. The aim should be to minimize the modifiable and preventable risk factors as much as possible.

Optimizing the Preventable Risk Factors

Smoking- The risk of infection increases significantly in smokers post-surgery, smoking impairs the reparative process of wound healing by affecting tissue oxygenation, Sorensen et al conducted a randomized control trial with 78 healthy subjects and noted a significant difference in postoperative infection with a 12% occurrence in smokers and 2% in non-smokers, abstinence from smoking four weeks before surgery reduces the risk of post-operative infection. ^[14]

Preoperative Glucose Monitoring- High blood glucose level has a detrimental effect on wound healing as it inhibits keratinocytes and fibroblast migration which causes an increase in the biofilm formation of S Aureus. HBA1C level of 7% or less minimizes the chances of developing post-operative infections. A tight glycemic index should be maintained for patients before surgery. ^[15]

Screening and Eradication of S Aureus.

Staphylococcus aureus (S Aureus) is the most common organism that has been isolated at the surgical site infections. The main reason for this is the presence of S Aureus as the normal flora of the human body, most commonly seen in the nose, respiratory tract, and skin. It has many virulence factors that promote the formation of biofilm and attachment to the host tissue converting it into nutrients required for bacterial growth. In a study of 7019 who were screened for S Aureus before elective orthopedic surgery, 22.6% were found to have a Methicillin Sensitive S Aureus (MSSA) strain and 4.4% had a Methicillin Resistant S Aureus strain (MRSA). MRSA carriers showed a higher occurrence of SSI as compared to MSSA (0.97% vs 0.14%). They were later managed with 2% mupirocin ointment twice daily and chlorhexidine wash once daily for 5 days and a reduction of 59% in SSI was seen. ^[16]

Antiseptic shower and Dressings

A bactericidal effect is seen when the positively charged Chlorhexidine cation binds to the negatively charged bacterial cell wall disrupting the wall. In a study conducted by Edminston et al ^[17], he came up with a 2-shower regimen that includes 118ml of 4% chlorhexidine solution per shower and a one-minute pause before rinsing the solution off, this regimen kills maximum gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. A chlorhexidine no-rinse cloth application method has also been suggested as an effective method to reduce SSI. ^[18]

Intraoperative Preventive Methods to reduce POI Intravenous Antibiotics

A broad-spectrum antibiotic prophylactic dose 30 minutes before skin incision with redosing every four hours for longer surgeries has been shown to reduce the occurrence of SSI. The most commonly used antibiotic is cefazolin and patients with allergies to cefazolin or penicillin are administered clindamycin. [19]

Skin Preparation with antiseptic solution

Chlorhexidine gluconate and povidone-iodine with or without alcohol, are the most commonly used antiseptic solution for skin preparation. Some studies have shown an increased efficacy of these solutions with the addition of alcohol. [20]

Irrigation of the Wound

Intraoperatively, irrigating the surgical site before the incision is closed reduces the risk of POI. In a study conducted by Watanbe et al, [21] 223 patients were observed. Continuous saline irrigation with a mean speed of 2000 mL per hour showed a very significant reduction of SSI. Another solution that can be used for irrigation is Povidone iodine. In a study conducted by Cheng et al, out of 244 patients 120 were administered Povidone iodine solution and the remaining 124 with normal saline. Patients with PVP-I showed a reduced infection rate. PVP-I has sometimes shown cytotoxic effects in some animal studies and hence chlorhexidine gluconate is a safer alternative to normal saline for wound irrigation till further studies are done to establish the use of povidone-iodine as an irrigating solution. [22]

Oxygenation and Regulation of Body Temperature

Continuous perfusion of the tissue during surgery combined with delivery of fraction-inspired oxygen (FiO₂) increases the viability of the tissue and accelerates wound healing. Inanmaz et al conducted a study with 42 patients who had undergone neuromuscular scoliosis surgery. Hyperbaric oxygen was administered to the patients after the surgery and those who received the oxygen therapy showed lower infection rates. However, the amount of fraction-inspired oxygen should be moderated as higher amounts can lead to cellular damage and apoptosis. Since the normal FiO₂ range in air is 21%, not more than 50% oxygen should be administered to the patients undergoing surgery. A decrease in body temperature is associated with increased POI and hence warming of the patients and maintaining the temperature between 36.5C and 37.5C is advisable. [23]

Post-Operative Preventive Measures

Silver-Impregnated Dressings

Silver has antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative pathogens. The toxicity of silver is considerably lower in humans as compared to bacteria and hence it can be used to reduce the risk of wound infections after surgery. In a study conducted by Epstein et al, he compared silver-impregnated dressings with regular dressing and observed that none of the patients who received the silver-impregnated dressings developed any superficial or deep wound infections. (24)

Closed Incision Negative-Pressure Wound Therapy

Closed incision negative pressure wound therapy (CI-NPWT) has been shown to reduce the tensile forces of edema and enhance the removal of exudate. It also increases the blood and the lymphatic flow around the wound, thereby providing a positive impact on the wound. In a study conducted by Adogwa et al, the control group that did not receive CI-N PWT had a higher incidence of postoperative SSI. [25]

Management of Postoperative Infections

An early identification of POIs plays a crucial role in its management. Diagnosis typically involves clinical evaluation, laboratory tests (e.g., complete blood count, cultures), and imaging studies if necessary. Empirical antibiotic therapy should be initiated based on common pathogens and the surgical site. Treatment should be adjusted based on culture results and sensitivities. In certain cases where abscess formation is seen, surgical intervention in the form of drainage may be necessary. Debridement of necrotic tissue is often essential for effective treatment. Supportive care in the form of pain management should be provided. Nutritional support and hydration can facilitate recovery. [25]

Follow-Up Care:

Regular follow-ups help to assess wound healing and detect any complications early. Adjust care plans based on the patient's recovery progress. [25]

CONCLUSION:

Postoperative infections remain a significant concern in surgical practice, with implications for patient health and healthcare systems. By understanding the causes and risk factors associated with POIs and implementing robust prevention and management strategies, healthcare providers can significantly reduce the incidence of these infections. Continuous education, adherence to protocols, and a focus on

patient-centered care are essential to enhance surgical outcomes and patient safety.

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